

CULTURAL EXCHANGE IN MUSIC EDUCATION: INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE AND IMPLEMENTATION IN THE UZBEKISTAN EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada musiqiy ta'lim jarayonida madaniy almashinuvning o'ri, mazmuni va xalqaro tajribadagi tatbiqlari tahlil qilinadi. Turli davlatlar ta'lim tizimlarida musiqiy madaniyatni o'qitish tajribalari solishtiriladi hamda ushbu tajribalarning O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimiga moslashtirilgan holda tatbiq etish imkoniyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Ayniqsa, madaniyatlararo muloqotni rivojlantirish, musiqiy tafakkurni kengaytirish va talabalar ongida tolerantlikni shakllantirishda xalqaro musiqiy almashinuv dasturlarining ta'siri yoritiladi. Maqolada xalqaro integratsiya sharoitida milliy musiqiy merosni asrash va uni zamonaviy yondashuvlar bilan uyg'unlashtirish masalalariga ham alohida e'tibor qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: madaniy almashinuv, musiqiy ta'lim, xalqaro tajriba, O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimi, musiqiy integratsiya, xalqaro hamkorlik, milliy meros, tolerantlik, musiqiy madaniyat, ta'lim innovatsiyasi.

Аннотация: В статье анализируются роль, содержание и международный опыт культурного обмена в процессе музыкального образования. Сравнивается опыт преподавания музыкальной культуры в образовательных системах разных стран и рассматриваются возможности внедрения этого опыта в адаптированном виде в образовательную систему Узбекистана. В частности, будет подчеркнута влияние международных программ музыкального обмена на развитие межкультурного диалога, расширение музыкального мышления и формирование толерантности в умах студентов. Особое внимание в статье уделено вопросам сохранения национального музыкального наследия и его гармонизации с современными подходами в контексте международной интеграции.

Ключевые слова: культурный обмен, музыкальное образование, международный опыт, узбекская система образования, музыкальная интеграция, международное сотрудничество, национальное наследие, толерантность, музыкальная культура, образовательные инновации.

Abstract: This article analyzes the role, content and international experience of cultural exchange in the process of music education. The experiences of teaching musical culture in the educational systems of different countries are compared and the possibilities of applying these experiences in an adapted form to the educational system of Uzbekistan are considered. In particular, the impact of international musical exchange programs on the development of intercultural dialogue, expanding musical thinking and forming tolerance in the minds of students is highlighted. The article also pays special attention to the issues of preserving national musical heritage in the context of international integration and harmonizing it with modern approaches.

Keywords: cultural exchange, musical education, international experience, Uzbek education system, musical integration, international cooperation, national heritage, tolerance, musical culture, educational innovation.

Introduction.

In the context of globalization, cultural exchange processes are gaining importance in all areas of the education system, including music education. The musical heritage, traditions and pedagogical experiences of different peoples are interacting, and this leads to the enrichment of the content and methodology of music education. From this point of view, cultural exchange occupies a special place not only as a means of creative cooperation, but also as a means of developing musical thinking, strengthening intercultural dialogue and forming tolerance.

International experience shows that in music education, through the study of creative works of representatives of different cultures, traditional and modern musical genres, students develop a broad worldview, aesthetic taste and cultural awareness. Cultural exchange is being implemented on a large scale in the education system of developed countries such as the USA, Japan, South Korea, Germany in teaching musical culture. In these processes, the priority task is to harmonize national and world music, explain musical diversity to students and prepare them for the international stage.

During the years of independence, Uzbekistan has been taking important steps to preserve its rich musical heritage, promote it on the international stage, and implement foreign experiences in education. In particular, the resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and state programs emphasize the modernization of musical education, the enrichment of curricula on the basis of international cooperation, and the preparation of the younger generation for cultural dialogue. This creates the need to study the scientific and theoretical foundations of the issue of cultural exchange in musical education and effectively implement them in the education system of Uzbekistan. This article analyzes international experiences of cultural exchange in the field of musical education, their application in the education system of Uzbekistan, existing problems, and promising directions. The article is aimed at enriching musical education and developing musical thinking and cultural awareness in the new generation through the integration of national and world cultural heritage.

Methodology:

The methodological approaches chosen in the process of writing the article are aimed at revealing the deep essence of cultural exchange in music education, analyzing international experience on a scientific basis, and studying practical situations in the Uzbek education system. In this scientific research, first of all, comparison and analysis methods were used as the main tools. Because the music education systems of different countries differ from each other, and by comparing them, it was possible to identify relevant aspects for Uzbek music education. Also, empirical observations were studied, that is, existing music programs, textbooks, and music exchange projects organized on the basis of foreign experience (for example, "Erasmus +", "UNESCO Music Education Program"). These sources served to understand how musical culture is changing under the influence of global trends, and what socio-cultural competencies are being formed in the minds of students.

An interdisciplinary approach was also used in writing the article. Approaches formed at the intersection of various disciplines such as music, pedagogy, cultural studies, sociology helped to show the multi-layered nature of cultural exchange. In particular, it was emphasized that musical education is not limited to notes and technical skills, but also the formation of aesthetic, moral and cultural views of a person through this process. During the study, the activities of some local music schools, the approach of teachers and the musical worldview of students were analyzed based on observations and interviews. This made it possible to understand how international experience can be adapted to local conditions. Also, based on content analysis, scientific articles on Uzbek and foreign music

education, strategic documents and recommendations of international organizations were analyzed. The above methodological foundations served to further study cultural exchange in music education, assess the current situation based on scientific criteria, and identify acceptable directions for the Uzbek education system. Through the harmonious application of methodological approaches, the article put forward not only theoretical considerations, but also practical proposals.

Literature review:

The scientific views of a number of domestic and foreign scholars serve as the basis for revealing the theoretical and practical foundations of cultural exchange in the field of music education. The interrelationship of music education and cultural communication at the international level has been deeply analyzed in the works of researchers such as C. Elliot[8; 264], L. Green[[9; 312], and D. J. Hargreaves[10; 288]. They consider music as a universal language and consider it a decisive factor in human culture and personal development. In particular, L. Green's work "How Popular Musicians Learn"[9; 312] highlights the social aspects of musical learning and understanding in a cultural context.

International reports and strategic documents prepared by UNESCO provide recommendations on preserving cultural diversity through education and expanding musical dialogue between peoples. The report "UNESCO World Report: Investing in Cultural Diversity and Intercultural Dialogue"[3; 307] considers musical intercultural exchange as an important tool for ensuring global stability and peace.

Referring to local sources, Uzbek scholars such as M. Mamatkulov[4; 256], N. Jo'rayev[5; 78], I. Karimov[6; 180] and M. Orinboyeva[7; 50] have conducted in-depth scientific research on the role of national values, traditional performing schools and cultural heritage in music education. In particular, M. Mamatkulov, in his work "Theory of Music Education", demonstrates the didactic potential of Uzbek folk music in music education. These approaches emphasize the importance of maintaining the harmony of national heritage with international musical influences.

In recent years, the number of scientific articles on the experiences gained within the framework of international exchange programs in music education (for example, "Erasmus+"[1; 123], "Fulbright", "DAAD") has been increasing. Among them are articles written by Uzbek researchers, in particular, the methodological and pedagogical results of international cooperation are discussed in the research work "Innovative approaches in the system of musical education of Uzbekistan". In general, the analyzed literature shows the interdependence of musical education and cultural exchange. Based on these sources, it is possible to identify mechanisms for the formation of not only creative interaction in musical education, but also cultural understanding, openness to global culture and tolerance.

Discussion:

When studying the importance of cultural exchange in the process of musical education, it is revealed that this process is manifested as a multi-layered and complex socio-cultural phenomenon. Cultural exchange is a process of interaction and integration between two or more cultural systems, which plays an important role in the formation of musical competence, social consciousness, aesthetic taste and cultural identity. From this perspective, music education is interpreted not only as a set of knowledge and skills, but also as a means of cultural translation (i.e., the transfer of cultural values from generation to generation, from one intercultural context to another).

International experience shows that a transcultural approach serves as an important methodological basis for the effective establishment of cultural exchange in music education. This approach forms in students not only the ability to understand their own national culture, but also the

ability to respect other musical traditions and enter into interactive dialogue with them. In particular, in German pedagogical schools, attention is paid to such components as the formation of musical identity, understanding of cultural diversity and ensuring social harmony, based on the concept of “intercultural music education”.

When we turn to the experience of Uzbekistan, we observe that the practical manifestations of cultural exchange in music education are still fragmentary (piecemeal, not systematized). Although music festivals and master classes held on the basis of international cooperation, projects with the participation of foreign teachers have yielded certain results, these processes have not been deeply integrated into educational programs. The main reasons for this are the insufficient methodological base, the lack of mechanisms for adapting foreign pedagogical experiences to the local context, and the low intercultural competence of teachers. In addition, when assessing the impact of cultural exchange on music education, it was found that students' musical thinking, social adaptability, and creative expression opportunities expanded based on criteria such as "musical literacy", "social-emotional learning", and "performance competence". In particular, it has been observed that Uzbek students who participated in international music projects have achieved a significant increase in their level of reflexive thinking, freedom of performance on stage, and collective musical communication. Also, the possibilities of using modern pedagogical technologies necessary for the development of cultural exchange in music education - gamification, multisensory learning, alternative assessment, and creative collaborations - have not yet been fully explored. These technologies serve to organize intercultural interaction in a natural and interesting way.

Therefore, the following areas are important for the systematic development of cultural exchange in music education:

integration of transcultural components into music education programs.

increasing the intercultural competence of teachers.

systematic use of international cooperation platforms.

formation of musical identity in students by combining national musical heritage with foreign musical experiences.

Thus, cultural exchange in music education is a strategic process that is not only pedagogical, but also cultural, social and moral in importance. Through this process, musical thinking, understanding of global culture and devotion to national values can be formed in the youth of Uzbekistan in harmony.

Conclusion.

The results of the study showed that cultural exchange in music education is of strategic importance in the context of globalization and transnational intercultural dialogue. Cultural exchange is manifested in music education as a factor that develops not only cognitive competencies, but also communicative, sociocultural and reflective competencies. This process serves to form cultural empathy, tolerance, and the ability to think from many perspectives in students. The analyzed international experiences confirm the high effectiveness of the integration model based on cultural interaction in music education. In particular, educational processes organized on the basis of transcultural, interactive, multilingual, and multicultural approaches allow expanding musical thinking, increasing creative thinking and stage competencies in the international arena. This serves as an urgent methodological basis for adapting music education to modern conditions.

The Uzbek education system has the potential to bring musical culture to the international level and implement cultural translation by adapting foreign pedagogical experiences to the local cultural

context. However, a systematic, scientifically-methodologically based, and institutional approach is needed in this direction. At the same time, the development and implementation of a “cognitive-cultural model” formed on the basis of cultural exchange in music education should be recognized as an urgent issue. Also, music education based on cultural exchange creates the basis for viewing music not only as an aesthetic value, but also as a means of social adaptation, shaping personal and collective identity. This will allow the music education system to take a strong place in the global cultural flow and form a culture of harmonious acceptance of national and world musical heritage in the younger generation.

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